
A Geographical Analysis Of Spatio Temporal Senerio Of Canal Irrigation In Sangli District

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Abstract:

Irrigation is a primary input for agricultural production. If an area is facilitated with the irrigation water agricultural sector is positively affected. Irrigation is an important determinant that affects directly as well as indirectly on agricultural technology. Irrigation is the lifeline of the modern agricultural system. In point of this present research paper researcher tries to find out changes in Canal irrigation to net irrigated area of the study region. The collection of data from the field have been compiled, processed and investigated with the help of some statistical methods represented with the help of maps. The proportion of canal irrigation to the net irrigated area as a whole district has 26.80 per cent in 1991, it is constantly increased up to 29.01 per cent in 2018, but the spatial distribution of canal irrigation varies from tahsil to tahsil. Therefore, the government should give up top the priority to develop the irrigation facilities in the Eastern and Southern parts of the district in its plan and policies in order to encourage agricultural technology.

Key words: *Canal Irrigation, Net Irrigated Area, Absolute Change.*

Introduction:

The economic base of the country depends on agriculture. In order to increase the agriculture yield, one should not depend upon rainfall alone but also depends on the irrigation. Irrigation is an important determinant that affects directly as well as indirectly on agricultural technology. Irrigation is the lifeline of the modern agricultural system. For the development of agriculture, secure irrigation is essential (Mansoor Ali, 2007). Irrigation plays a leading role in diminishing the adverse influence of scanty and highly unreliable rainfall. Such a role acquires an added significance in the dry lands where it becomes impossible to grow crops without irrigation (Singh and Dhillon, 1987).

Study Area:

Sangli District located between 16⁰, 45'N to 17⁰, 33'N latitude & 73⁰, 42'E to 75⁰, 40'E longitude. It lies in drought-prone area. It covers area of 8572 sq.km, it is 2.51% of Maharashtra state & population is about 28.22 Lakh (2011 census). Administratively it is divided into ten tahsils. In the study region most important rivers are Krishna, Warna, Morna, Yerala, Agrani, Man, etc. The study region rainfall decreases rapidly towards western part of district to eastern part of district. The climate of the Sangli district is generally hot and dry. The region has complexity in topography. It contains hilly region, river basins & undulating land of eastern side.

Figure No. 1

Objectives:

1. To analyse the spatio temporal study of canal irrigation in the study region.

Database and Methodology:

In the case of the present study, the secondary data has been collected from different Government offices like talhsil offices of Sangli District, Economics and Statistics Office Sangli District, Irrigation Department offices of Sangli district, Socio-Economic review of Sangli District. The collection of data from the field and offices have been compiled, processed and investigated with the help of some statistical methods represented with the help of maps and diagrams.

The Intensity of Irrigation:

The Intensity of Irrigation

$$= \frac{\text{Net Irrigated Area}}{\text{Net Sown Area}} \times 100$$

Spatial Distribution of Canal Irrigation:

Table No.1 reveals that the proportion of canal irrigation to the net irrigated area as a whole district has 26.80 per cent in 1991, it is constantly increased up to 29.01 per cent in 2018, but the spatial distribution of canal irrigation varies from talhsil to talhsil. Therefore, the study region has been divided into three categories on the basis of mean and standard deviation viz. high (i.e. above mean +SD), moderate (i.e.

ranging from mean to mean + SD) and low (i.e. below mean)

In 1991, the high proportion of canal irrigation i.e. above 46.38 per cent was recorded in Shirala, and Tasgaon talhsils due to located in Warna, Krishna and Yerela river basins and development of Warna and Morana irrigation project whereas Tasgaon talhsil is located in dry area but the development of Aarfal Storage Project, Krishna-Koyana Lift Irrigation- Takari, and Mhaisal Scheme and Tembhu irrigation scheme resulted in high area under canal irrigation. The moderate proportion of canal irrigation i.e. ranging from 25.86 to 46.38 per cent was noted only in Miraj talhsil.

Table No.1: Talhsil-wise Percentage of Area under Canal irrigation to Net Irrigated Area in Sangli District, 1991-2018

SN	Talhsils	1991	2018	Absolute Change
1	Shirala	59.03	37.61	-21.42
2	Walwa	20.95	26.96	6.01
3	Palus	-	-	-
4	Kadegaon	-	-	-
5	Khanapur	2.88	28.95	26.08
6	Atpadi	21.46	21.67	0.21
7	Tasgaon	50.53	27.29	-23.24
8	Miraj	40.99	28.91	-12.07
9	Kavathe Mahankal	1.55	27.16	25.60
10	Jath	9.50	33.92	24.42
Sangli District		26.80	29.01	2.20
Mean		25.86	28.87	3.20
SD		20.52	4.53	19.39

Source: Socio-Economic Abstract of Sangli District, 1991-2018.

The low proportion of canal irrigation i.e. below 25.86 per cent was registered in Walwa, Khanapur, Atpadi, Kavathe Mahankal and Jath talhsils due to Walwa, Khanapur and Atpadi talhsil is located in hilly area and rugged topography

while Kavathe Mahankal and Jath tahsils located in drought-prone area and scanty rainfall, therefore, there are low development of canal irrigation.

As per 2018, Table No.1 shows that the high proportion of canal irrigation i.e. above 33.40 per cent is recorded in Shirala and Jath tahsils due to the development of the Warna Project and Morana irrigation project in Shirala tahsil while Diddanala and Sankh irrigation project in Jath tahsil.

Figure No. 2

Figure No. 3

The moderate proportion of canal irrigation i.e. ranging between 28.87 to 33.40 per cent is noted in Khanapur and Miraj tahsils. The low proportion of canal irrigation i.e. below 28.87 per cent registered in Walwa, Atpadi, Tasgaon, and Kavathe Mahankal tahsils and causes are the same as mentioned earlier.

Absolute Change in Canal Irrigation:

Table No.1, designates that the district as a whole has 2.20 positive change in percentage of canal irrigation from 1991 to 2011. Table No.1, reveals that the positive

and negative change in canal irrigation in the study region. But the spatial distribution varies from tahsil to tahsil.

The high positive change in canal irrigation i.e. above 22.59 per cent is registered in Khanapur, Kavathe Mahankal and Jath tahsil due to the development of major lift irrigation schemes, medium projects, and Kolhapur type wires. The low positive change in canal irrigation i.e. below 22.59 per cent is found in Walwa tahsil while Atpadi tahsils due to the already development of surface irrigation in Walwa tahsil and hilly and undulating topography in Atpadi tahsil.

Figure No. 4

Table No.1, reveals that the negative change in the canal irrigation is noted only in Shirala, Tasgaon and Miraj tahsils. Because development of surface irrigation as a resulted in area under canal irrigation increased but the proportion of canal irrigation declined leads to the increased groundwater table and resulted in increased the number of wells and area under well irrigation.

Conclusion:

Irrigation is the most important requirement in the package practices for intensive and efficient cultivation of the high yielding varieties and also for multiple cropping, whereas without irrigation chemical fertilizers, costly inputs cannot be used with an advantage to the farmers. In the study region observed that the application of

irrigation water helps in stabilizing production under ceteris paribus conditions.

Therefore, the government should give up top the priority to develop the irrigation facilities in the Eastern and Southern parts of the district in its plan and policies in order to encourage agricultural technology and improve agricultural productivity. The minor irrigation projects should be planned at the micro-level as poor peasant will be the major beneficiaries in the drought-prone area of the district.

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